

The Looper Living Labs as blueprints for co-creation

The diverse solutions co-designed by local citizens led to an improvement of liveability and promoted mutual learning.

▶ In **Brussels**, residents co-designed solutions to traffic safety problems and a school improved its pupils' safety by closing off the street in front of the school every morning.

▶ In **Manchester**, the residents of the Brunswick neighbourhood proposed, co-designed and implemented traffic calming measures, a street mural, street planting, domestic plant baskets and welcome signs and banners.

▶ In **Verona**, local actors collaborated to improve air quality, liveability of urban spaces, and to reduce noise pollution. Long-term solutions such as increasing the area of existing parks with urban forests were also set in motion.

Would you like to find out how you can improve your neighbourhood with Looper?

For more information and to access the detailed Looper guidelines, please visit our website:

www.looperproject.eu

Here you can find:

- ▶ Detailed guidelines on how to set up and implement a co-creation process using learning loops.
- ▶ Guidelines for participatory measurements and visualization for air quality, traffic and noise.
- ▶ A database of co-design tools.
- ▶ Detailed insights into the do's and don'ts of co-creation from the three Looper Living Labs.

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How can our kids get to school in safety?

Where are all the buses?

How can we communicate our needs and dreams to our local government representatives?

How to provide better services at lower cost?

How to find out more about what the community needs?

Are you asking similar questions in your neighborhood? Looper can help you find the answers.

What is Looper?

The **Looper Model** is a set of methods and tools to support local co-creation. It works with 'learning loops,' which bring together local knowledge with local decision-making. The **Looper Toolkit** comprises online and offline tools to support the learning loops.

Three **Looper Living Labs** in Brussels, Manchester and Verona developed and tested the Model and Toolkit. All this helps to keep people 'in the loop', and to 'close the loop' so that local knowledge can lead to local action.

The Looper Model can help with practical solutions for air quality, noise, traffic safety, security, greenspace and other challenges in the public realm.

Learning loops

A **learning loop** is about building the community-based knowledge and creative thinking, which can turn problems into solutions. Each learning loop has three main stages:

Problem identification identify the issue, set up citizen monitoring, visualize and analyse data.

Monitoring together with citizens using low-cost devices has helped to improve the understanding of issues and monitor the impact of the interventions.

Co-design create options and decide which should be implemented.

An online platform visualised the collected data. The impacts of co-designed ideas on sustainability and stakeholders were evaluated using multi-actor multi-criteria analysis (MAMCA).

Action and feedback make real improvements (physical or social) and monitor impact.

Citizens co-designed solutions using online idea-generation tools as well as face-to-face meetings. Researchers were engaged in active outreach and were involved in local activities and networks.